

TENSILE STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOUR OF MULTIAXIAL METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional, cross-ply and angle-ply titanium metal matrix composite laminates have been fabricated using titanium alloy foils and two types of SiC fibre. The stress-strain behaviour of the different TMC layups are presented and discussed in relation to features observed on the fracture surfaces. A simple model utilising experimental data has been used to predict cross-ply and quasi-isotropic tensile behaviour based on measured mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is significant potential for reducing weight in such applications as satellite propellant tanks where methods for reducing satellite launch mass whilst increasing tank structural stiffness is of great interest to the space industry. Polymer composite overwrap tanks are becoming more widespread and have proven that weight savings in the aerospace industry are worth the additional cost and manufacturing complexity. However, polymer composites are not necessarily well suited to satellite propellant tanks where monolithic titanium liners are required for chemical compatibility. On the other hand, titanium alloy metal matrix composites (MMC) provide the possibility of providing enhanced structural stiffness and chemical compatibility. The design of such relatively complex structures using titanium MMCs requires the behaviour of cross-ply and angle-ply MMC layups to be understood.

In this work, various layups of titanium Ti-3Al-2.5V alloy matrix MMCs have been fabricated using 100 μm and 140 μm diameter TISICS SiC monofilament fibres, in a solid-state HIP foil-fibre process. A broad characterisation programme has been carried out to assess the mechanical properties of these fabricated materials at ambient temperature. In this paper, the tensile behaviour of a range of composite layups is presented.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Coupon manufacture and testing

Ti-3-2.5 (also commonly referred to as 'Grade 9' titanium) is an alpha-beta alloy, readily available in cold-rolled foil form; Ti-3-2.5 was selected due to similar (albeit lower) mechanical properties to Ti-6-4. Two types of silicon fibre were used, SM3156 and SM1140+. The SM3156 fibre (diameter 140 μm) has a higher strength (see Table 1) derived from its near stoichiometric/carbon-rich SiC monofilament as opposed to the SM1140+ (diameter 100 μm) which has a stoichiometric/silicon-rich structure. An SEM micrograph of the SM3156 fibre is shown in Fig. 1. Once laid up inside a standard HIP can, the fugitive binder used to maintain consistent fibre spacing was removed through a suitable

degas cycle and a proprietary HIP cycle was used to achieve consolidation between the sheets of aligned fibre and foils; no porosity was observed in specimens taken for metallographic preparation.

The orientations of coupons tested included monolithic Ti-3-2.5, uniaxial $[0]_8$, transverse $[90]_8$, cross-ply $[0/90]_{2s}$, angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ and quasi-isotropic $[0,-45,90,45]_s$. Fig. 2 shows the coupon dimensions used for the tests. For most tests, dog-bone shaped specimens were electro-discharge machined (using a FANUC wire eroder) into standard TISICS dogbone profiles from the parent material panels. The specimens were 170 mm long with dog-bone shoulder-to-gauge region transition having a radius of curvature of 420 mm. The coupons edges were ground to remove the recast layer at the cut surface as well as any possible machining defects. Successively fine grades of wetted SiC paper were then used to produce a uniform edge finish.

The width of the coupons was nominally 10 mm and the effective gauge length was 25 mm. The only exception was that the angle-ply coupons were also fabricated in a parallel sided coupon design with constant (larger) 20 mm gauge width in order to determine the magnitude of a possible edge effect from exposed fibre ends along the sample edges. Each coupon consisted of eight plies of fibre and nine sheets of grade 9 titanium foil diffusion bonded to give a nominal volume fraction of 32%. Specimen thicknesses for the SM1140+ and the SM3156 were approximately 1.4 mm and 1.9 mm, respectively. Bevelled aluminium end tabs (40 mm long by 12 mm wide, with a 9° bevel) were bonded to the specimens using a high strength structural adhesive (3M Scotchweld 9323 B/A), cured at a temperature of 80°C in a temperature controlled oven for one hour. Strain gauges were used to monitor axial and transverse strains in the coupon gauge length. Tensile tests were carried out using an electro-mechanical Instron 4505 test frame with 5500 series software at a cross-head displacement rate of 2 mm min^{-1} .

Figure 1: TISICS SM3156 SiC monofilament.

Figure 2: TISICS dogbone coupon design (all dimensions in mm).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Introduction

Four coupons were tested for each layup and fibre type (with the exception of the wider angle-ply coupons where only two of each fibre type were tested, and the SM3156 quasi-isotropic coupon where only three specimens were available). Stress-strain curves were plotted and modulus and failure stress and strain were extracted from each. Table 1 shows the tensile data for the monolithic specimens tested and the two fibre types while Tables 2 and 3 show the MMC data for the SM1140+ and the SM3156 fibres respectively. As can be seen in Tables 2 and 3, reasonable repeatability between a given fibre type and layup was obtained.

3.2 Monolithic Ti-3-2.5

The monolithic titanium alloy coupons were prepared in the same manner as the MMCs. A panel approximately 1.4 mm in thickness, consisting of ten diffusion-bonded Ti-3-2.5 foils, was cut into four coupons. Post-HIP, material from the panel was prepared for metallographic examination and found to have a microstructure similar to that of annealed condition Ti-3-2.5 with an equiaxed alpha microstructure containing small amounts of intergranular beta. The tensile stress-strain response of the monolithic coupons, see Fig. 3, was linear until the macroscopic yield point at around 0.5% strain, a clear yield point was observed at ~500 MPa followed by a significant reduction in instantaneous modulus after which strain hardening was evident. Due to the limitations of the strain gauges used, strain could only be measured to 5%; estimates using the crosshead displacement data showed that failure of the monolithic material occurred at strains approaching 13%. Failure of the coupon began with plastic deformation in a localised region of the gauge, leading to necking. Post failure, the ductile ‘cup and cone’ type fracture surfaces were inspected under SEM and evidence of ductile fracture by void coalescence was found.

Figure 3: The tensile stress strain behaviour of monolithic foil-bonded Ti-3-2.5.

3.3 0° layup

Fig. 4 shows the stress-strain behaviour of a $[0]_8$ laminate with SM3156 fibres and key data for both fibre type MMCs presented in Tables 2 and 3 (the graphs for the SM1140+ fibre are not shown here). The $[0]_8$ laminates show a linear stress-strain response until about 0.3%, with a pronounced knee in the stress-strain curve at about 0.4% strain. The knee in the 0° specimens is a result of matrix yielding. This occurs at slightly lower levels of strain than in the matrix alone and the probable reason for this is the residual stresses induced in the MMC during cooling placing the matrix in tension in the unloaded state. Once the matrix has yielded, its contribution to the instantaneous modulus is negligible and the behaviour is fibre-dominated up to failure (the stress-strain curve is therefore linear again after the knee). Catastrophic failure resulted when the fibres fail. The SM3156 $[0]_8$ fracture surfaces were seen to occur at 45° to the loading direction. These observations may support suggestions by other researchers as to fracture mechanisms in MMCs [1, 2, 3].

Debonding of the interfacial region is not believed to be a significant process in the failure as no significant fibre pull-out was observed on the fracture surfaces and this implies reasonable bonding of fibre to matrix [4] (Fig. 5). Little difference was noted between the behaviour of the two fibre types, with the exception of an increased modulus and UTS for the SM3156 composite and this would be expected as the SM3156 fibre modulus is slightly higher than the SM1140+ fibre. In both cases, the matrix showed signs of ductility through a dimpled appearance. The Voigt rule of mixtures, gave close predictions of modulus (201 GPa and 182 GPa) for the SM3156 and SM1140+ unidirectional composites when appropriate properties were used, as shown in Table 1.

Figure 4: Stress-strain behavior of SM3156 [0]₈, [90]₈ and [0/90]_{2s} laminates; a prediction of the behavior of a [0/90]_{2s} laminate based on the rule-of-mixtures is also shown.

Figure 5: An SEM micrograph of the unidirectional SM3156 MMC fracture surface.

3.4 90° layup

The stress-strain response of the SM3156 fibre specimens are shown in Fig. 4 and mechanical properties for both fibre types are presented in Tables 2 and 3. For the $[90]_8$ laminate, non-linearity begins at much lower strains (about 0.15%) with a plateau in the stress-strain curve from about 1%. The region where non-linearity first occurs is expected around 0.15% strain due to interfacial debonding arising at low stress levels (as shown in [5, 6]). The interfacial bond between the pyrolytic carbon fibre coating and titanium matrix is inherently weak and this results in a poor initial transverse yield strength. At the point of interfacial debonding, the matrix essentially contains an array of holes which can act as stress risers; the matrix continues to plastically deform with no appreciable constraint or loading carrying from the fibres, and the instantaneous modulus falls rapidly until about 1% strain where a plateau occurs. Necking occurs between the matrix ligaments (Fig. 6) and this leads to a failure of the material where shear bands have formed. The formation of shear bands prior to failure has been observed by others [7]. The Reuss expression provides a good prediction (139 GPa; 4% error) to the initial modulus of the SM3156 fibre composite but overestimates the modulus of the SM1140+ fibre composite (134 GPa; 17% error):

Figure 6: SEM micrographs of a SM3156 transverse MMC fracture surface.

3.5 Cross-ply (0/90°) layup

Fig. 4 shows data for a $[0/90]_{2s}$ coupon with SM3156 fibres, and a prediction of the $[0/90]_{2s}$ coupon behaviour based on a rule-of-mixtures sum of the stresses of the $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ laminates at each value of applied strain. There is good agreement between the prediction and the SM3156 experimental data. The response of both 0° and 90° layups play a role in the tensile behaviour of the cross-ply laminate and the wide non-linear (knee) range for the stress strain graph (0.24 % to 0.6% strain) spans the values seen in the 90° and 0° specimens respectively. Final failure caused by fibre fracture results in failure strains that are broadly consistent with the 0° specimens at $\sim 1.1\%$. The specimen fracture surface is shown in Fig. 7. The carbon coating on the monofilaments is largely intact and none of the carbon coating has been left in the transverse channels which suggests that the carbon to SiC interfacial bond is stronger than that of the matrix to carbon bond. Classical laminate theory (CLT) has also been used to predict the modulus for both the cross-ply SM1140+ and the SM3156 MMCs. The results of the CLT analysis have been compared (Tables 4 and 5) to the values measured from test. As found with the rule of mixtures approach, CLT predictions overestimated the laminate moduli.

Figure 7: SEM micrograph of a cross-ply MMC fracture surface containing SM3156 fibres.

3.6 +/- 45° layup

The stress-strain response of the SM3156 fibre specimen is shown in Fig. 8 and mechanical properties for composites using both fibre types are presented in Tables 2 and 3. This MMC layup has not been as thoroughly examined in literature as axial and transverse layups due, in part, to the fact that many of the benefits of using SiC reinforcement are negated with such a layup where the matrix behaviour appears to dominate the composite stress-strain behaviour. However this may not be the case for angle-ply shafts, where performance can exceed monolithic titanium alloys. Although the modulus of the coupon is increased by the presence of fibres, a tendency for the fibres to rotate to align with the loading direction causes a ‘scissoring’ action leading to consequent necking of the gauge section under tension. The failure strain was found to be ~10% for this layup but an initial drop in instantaneous modulus occurs at ~0.15% strain. Laminated plate theory provided material modulus values for the two fibre types tested that were reasonably consistent with the measured data (Tables 4 and 5). This again suggests matrix dominated material properties. The fracture surface of the MMC sample was observed (Fig. 9) and most of the fibre fracture planes are perpendicular to the loading direction, with indications of matrix ductility.

Figure 8: Stress-strain behavior of SM3156 [0/90]_{2s}, [±45]_{2s} and [0,-45,90,45]_s laminates; a prediction of the behavior of a [0,-45,90,45]_s laminate based on the rule-of-mixtures is also shown.

Figure 9: SEM micrograph of an angle-ply MMC fracture surface containing SM3156 fibres.

3.7 Quasi-isotropic (0°, -45°, 90°, 45°): QI layup

The stress-strain response of the SM3156 fibre specimen is shown in Fig. 8 with mechanical property data for both fibre types presented in Tables 2 and 3. Few researchers have tested [0, -45, 90, 45]_s MMC specimens because limited applications have been identified for the QI layup. The stress strain behaviour in QI MMCs exhibits multistage failure, which has been commented on by others [8,9,10]. Non-linear behaviour for the composites tested here begins at about 0.12% strain, and then at 0.7% strain, some degree of linearity is recovered. Observation of the fracture surface (shown in Fig. 10) raises some points of interest. First, most of the -45° fibre fracture surfaces appear to be parallel to the composite fracture surface. Second, the (central) +45° degree layer fractured fibres appear recessed compared to the -45 fibres. It is possible that this is related to the direction of final failure across the coupon. CLT was once again used to predict the initial modulus of the QI laminates, although the predicted values were only 9% and 7% different from the measured SM1140+ and SM3156 test values respectively, this shows a greater disparity than the simple rule of mixtures prediction.

Figure 10: SEM micrograph of a quasi-isotropic MMC fracture surface containing SM3156 fibres.

Material	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)	E (GPa)
Ti-3Al-2.5V alloy	668 ± 4	> 5	106 ± 1
SM1140+ SiC fibre	3200 - 3600	≈ 1	330 - 360
SM3156 SiC fibre	3700 - 3900	1.6 - 1.8	400

Table 1: Mechanical property data for the matrix and the two SiC fibres.

Layup	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)	E (GPa)
[0] ₈	1400 ± 29	1.01 ± 0.04	188 ± 4
[90] ₈	486 ± 39	1.93 ± 0.45	111 ± 11
[0/90] _{2s}	957 ± 30	1.20 ± 0.04	119 ± 9
[±45] _{2s}	663	> 5	135 ± 1
[0/-45/90/+45] _s	623 ± 40	1.26 ± 0.10	126 ± 6

Table 2: Mechanical property data for the SM1140+ fibre and Ti-3Al-2.5V alloy matrix.

Layup	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)	E (GPa)
[0] ₈	1488 ± 11	0.93 ± 0.01	201 ± 3
[90] ₈	457 ± 3	1.95 ± 0.46	134 ± 13
[0/90] _{2s}	975 ± 20	1.05 ± 0.05	146 ± 6
[±45] _{2s}	666 ± 1	> 5	140 ± 1
[0/-45/90/+45] _s	731 ± 8	1.17 ± 0.07	137 ± 9

Table 3: Mechanical property data for the SM3156 fibre and Ti-3Al-2.5V alloy matrix.

Layup	E (GPa)	
	CLT	ACTUAL
[0/90] _{2s}	150	119 ± 9
[±45] _{2s}	123	135
[0/-45/90/+45] _s	137	126 ± 6

Table 4: Classical laminate theory predictions and measured properties for SM1140+ TMCs.

Input values used: $E_1 = 188$ GPa, $E_2 = 111$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$, $G_{12} = 45$ GPa.

Layup	E (GPa)	
	CLT	ACTUAL
[0/90] _{2s}	168	146 ± 6
[±45] _{2s}	126	140
[0/-45/90/+45] _s	148	137 ± 9

Table 5: Classical laminate theory predictions and measured properties for SM3156 TMCs.

Input values used: $E_1 = 201$ GPa, $E_2 = 134$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$, $G_{12} = 44$ GPa.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

An extensive range of MMC tensile testing has been undertaken, including unidirectional, cross-ply and angle-ply laminates, using two different fibre types. It has been found that a reasonable fit to experimental data for the stress-strain curves can be obtained through a weighted average rule-of-mixtures approach by combining the results from simpler laminates; in some cases, better predictions are likely to be possible when residual stresses are considered. Observations of the fracture surfaces have provided valuable insights into the failure mechanisms of the various laminates tested.

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